

Consent Form

This survey aims to better understand the influence of the global use of English on the work of translators and interpreters. The insights from this survey are expected to contribute to professional development and training programmes. It is in English and addresses professionals who have English as one of their working languages.

All answers will be treated confidentially.

Thank you!

The first item concerns your informed consent about providing answers in this questionnaire. Please read the text below carefully. If you agree, please indicate this below and continue with the items and questions that follow. Answering the survey takes about 15 minutes. If you are not interested, please close your browser.

I freely and voluntarily consent to participate in this survey. I understand that I will not receive monetary payment for my participation. I understand that the purpose of this survey is to investigate interpreters' and translators' views about source texts in various settings and that I am free to discontinue my participation at any time.

I understand that all my responses are completely anonymous: no identifying information about me or my workplace will be captured unless I voluntarily offer additional personal or contact information in any of the comment fields. In addition, I understand that my responses will be combined with those of many others (so-called aggregation) and only presented in summary form in order to further protect my anonymity.

I also understand that if I would like more information about this survey or have any questions or concerns, I can contact Prof. Michaela Albi-Mikasa, Zurich University of Applied Sciences (albm@zhaw.ch).

I have read the information above and agree to participate in this research by answering the questions in this survey.

- Yes
 No

* must provide value

CLINT survey

This survey focuses on translators and interpreters who have English as one of their working languages. Most of the questions are optional, but we would appreciate hearing your responses to as many as possible.

Thank you!

You can adjust the font size by clicking on the + or - buttons underneath the A's in the top right of the screen.

You can save your answers and return later by clicking on the button Save & Return Later at the bottom of each page. Please do not forget to click Submit at the end of the survey.

Do you work as a translator and/or interpreter?

* must provide value

- Yes
 No

Is English one of your working languages?

* must provide value

- Yes
 No

Which age range do you fall into?

- 20 or younger
 21-25
 26-30
 31-35
 36-40
 41-45
 46-50
 51-55
 56-60
 61-65
 66-70
 over 70

What gender do you identify with?

- male
 female
 non-binary
 prefer not to specify

I have been working as a translator/interpreter for about:

- up to 5 years
 6-10 years
 11-15 years
 16-20 years
 21-25 years
 26-30 years
 31-35 years
 36-40 years
 41-45 years
 over 45 years

What percentage have you worked on average per year as a translator and/or interpreter over the past 5 years?

- under 20%
 20-39%
 40-59%
 60-79%
 80% or over

If you had to choose only one, which of the following best describes your primary occupation?

* must provide value

- conference interpreter
 community interpreter
 translator
 post-editor

Do you also sometimes do the work of any of the following?

- conference interpreter
- community interpreter
- specialist translator
- post-editor
- AVT translator
- literary translator
- post-editor
- court interpreter
- proof-reader

I am a member of the following professional associations:

- AIIC
- (a) national association(s)
- other

National association(s) (please specify):

Other (please specify):

In a typical year before the pandemic, I interpreted on this many days...

- 1 - 20
- 21 - 40
- 41 - 60
- 61 - 80
- 81 - 100
- more than 100

10%

What do you consider your first/native language?

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
- Hausa
- Hindi
- Hungarian
- Indonesian
- Irish
- Italian
- Japanese
- Javanese
- Korean
- Latvian
- Lithuanian
- Maithili
- Maltese
- Mandarin Chinese
- Marathi
- Montenegrin
- Odia
- Persian
- Polish
- Portuguese
- Romanian
- Romansh
- Russian
- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese

Do you have another native language?

- Yes. I have two native languages in total.
- Yes. I have three native languages in total.
- No.

What do you consider your other native language?

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
- Hausa
- Hindi
- Hungarian
- Indonesian
- Irish
- Italian
- Japanese
- Javanese
- Korean
- Latvian
- Lithuanian
- Maithili
- Maltese
- Mandarin Chinese
- Marathi
- Montenegrin
- Odia
- Persian
- Polish
- Portuguese
- Romanian
- Romansh
- Russian
- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese

What do you consider your other native language?

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
- Hausa
- Hindi
- Hungarian
- Indonesian
- Irish
- Italian
- Japanese
- Javanese
- Korean
- Latvian
- Lithuanian
- Maithili
- Maltese
- Mandarin Chinese
- Marathi
- Montenegrin
- Odia
- Persian
- Polish
- Portuguese
- Romanian
- Romansh
- Russian
- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other
- More than one

If (any of) your first/native language(s) is not included in the list(s) above, please enter it here: _____

The following questions relate to your working language combination(s). Please include English.

How many A-languages do you have?

- 1
- 2
- 3

A language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
- Hausa
- Hindi
- Hungarian
- Indonesian
- Irish
- Italian
- Japanese
- Javanese
- Korean
- Latvian
- Lithuanian
- Maithili
- Maltese
- Mandarin Chinese
- Marathi
- Montenegrin
- Odia
- Persian
- Polish
- Portuguese
- Romanian
- Romansh
- Russian
- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other

(Start typing the name of the language in English and the list will jump to the correct entry.)

Other A language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
- Hausa
- Hindi
- Hungarian
- Indonesian
- Irish
- Italian
- Japanese
- Javanese
- Korean
- Latvian
- Lithuanian
- Maithili
- Maltese
- Mandarin Chinese
- Marathi
- Montenegrin
- Odia
- Persian
- Polish
- Portuguese
- Romanian
- Romansh
- Russian
- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other

Other A language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
- Hausa
- Hindi
- Hungarian
- Indonesian
- Irish
- Italian
- Japanese
- Javanese
- Korean
- Latvian
- Lithuanian
- Maithili
- Maltese
- Mandarin Chinese
- Marathi
- Montenegrin
- Odia
- Persian
- Polish
- Portuguese
- Romanian
- Romansh
- Russian
- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other

If (any of) your A-language(s) is not included in the list(s) above, please enter it here: _____

How many B-languages do you have?

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

B language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
- Hausa
- Hindi
- Hungarian
- Indonesian
- Irish
- Italian
- Japanese
- Javanese
- Korean
- Latvian
- Lithuanian
- Maithili
- Maltese
- Mandarin Chinese
- Marathi
- Montenegrin
- Odia
- Persian
- Polish
- Portuguese
- Romanian
- Romansh
- Russian
- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other:

(Start typing the name of the language in English and the list will jump to the correct entry.)

Other B language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
- Hausa
- Hindi
- Hungarian
- Indonesian
- Irish
- Italian
- Japanese
- Javanese
- Korean
- Latvian
- Lithuanian
- Maithili
- Maltese
- Mandarin Chinese
- Marathi
- Montenegrin
- Odia
- Persian
- Polish
- Portuguese
- Romanian
- Romansh
- Russian
- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other:

Other B language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
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- Maltese
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- Montenegrin
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- Portuguese
- Romanian
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- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other:

Other B language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
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- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other:

Other B language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
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- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other:

If (any of) your B-language(s) is not included in the list(s) above, please enter it here: _____

How many C-languages do you have?

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

C language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
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- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other

(Start typing the name of the language in English and the list will jump to the correct entry.)

Other C language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
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- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other

Other C language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
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- Estonian
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- Swahili
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- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other

Other C language:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
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- Turkish
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- Urdu
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- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other

Other C language:

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- Odia
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- Romanian
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- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese
- Other

If (any of) your C-language(s) is not included in the list(s) above, please enter it here: _____

20%

I work in the following professional context(s):

- commercial/private market
- local authorities
- healthcare
- government
- international institutions
- NGO
- other

Other (please specify):

I work:

- as a freelancer
- as a staff member
- both

How many languages do you usually work into? If you work into your first/native language(s) please include them as well.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

Language(s) I usually work into:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
- Hausa
- Hindi
- Hungarian
- Indonesian
- Irish
- Italian
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- Javanese
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- Latvian
- Lithuanian
- Maithili
- Maltese
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- Marathi
- Montenegrin
- Odia
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- Portuguese
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- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese

If (any of) your language(s) is not included in the list, please enter it here: _____

How many languages do you usually work out of? If you work out of your first/native language(s) please include them as well.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

Language(s) I usually work out of:

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Bhojpuri
- Bosnian
- Bulgarian
- Croatian
- Czech
- Danish
- Dutch
- Eastern Punjabi
- English
- Estonian
- Finnish
- French
- German
- Greek
- Gujarati
- Hausa
- Hindi
- Hungarian
- Indonesian
- Irish
- Italian
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- Javanese
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- Russian
- Serbian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swahili
- Swedish
- Tamil
- Telugu
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Urdu
- Vietnamese
- Western Punjabi
- Wu Chinese
- Yue Chinese

If (any of) your language(s) is not included in the list, please enter it here: _____

30%

The following questions all relate to the source texts and/or talks in English that you deal with in your work setting.

How would you describe the difficulties you encounter most often in English texts/talks? Multiple answers are possible.

- unusual accent/spelling/punctuation
- infrequent vocabulary
- literary style
- register shifts
- vagueness
- unclear pronoun reference
- technical topic
- abstract topic
- complex sentence structures
- long sentences
- concepts non-existent/different in target culture
- technical terminology
- no lexical equivalents in target language
- puns/jokes/humor/idioms
- high delivery speed
- high information density
- complicated or complex text organization
- lack of logic
- other

Other (please specify):

What proportion of source texts/talks produced by native speakers of English would you consider poor?

- all
- the majority of them
- about half of them
- the minority of them
- none

How would you describe poor source texts produced by native speakers of English? Multiple answers are possible.

- unusual pronunciation
- incorrect spelling/punctuation
- odd word choice
- misuse of vocabulary
- odd style
- inappropriate register shifts
- lack of logic
- vagueness
- lack of cohesion
- poor organization
- unclear pronoun reference
- awkward sentence structures
- grammatical errors
- unconventional use of metaphors and/or concepts
- I don't know
- other

Other (please specify):

Are you provided with information beforehand about whether the producer of the source text/talk is a non-native speaker of English?

- always
- usually
- rarely
- no

Can you otherwise recognize whether a source text/talk has been produced by a native or a non-native speaker?

- always
- usually
- rarely
- no

In your experience, what proportion of the source texts/talks you usually deal with are produced by non-native speakers of English?

- all
- the majority of them
- about half of them
- the minority of them
- none
- not applicable

40%

What proportion of source texts/talks produced by non-native speakers of English would you consider poor?

- all
 the majority of them
 about half of them
 the minority of them
 none

How would you describe poor source texts produced by non-native speakers of English? Multiple answers are possible.

- unusual pronunciation
 incorrect spelling/punctuation
 odd word choice
 misuse of vocabulary
 odd style
 inappropriate register shifts
 lack of logic
 vagueness
 lack of cohesion
 poor organization
 unclear pronoun reference
 awkward sentence structures
 grammatical errors
 unconventional use of metaphors and/or concepts
 I don't know
 other

Other (please specify):

How would you describe the major difficulties of translating/interpreting source texts/talks produced by non-native speakers (max. 5)?

- unusual pronunciation
 incorrect spelling/punctuation
 odd word choice
 misuse of vocabulary
 odd style
 inappropriate register shifts
 lack of logic
 vagueness
 lack of cohesion
 poor organization
 unclear pronoun reference
 awkward sentence structures
 grammatical errors
 unconventional use of metaphors and/or concepts
 I don't know
 other

Other (please specify):

How do you cope with unusual pronunciation in a source talk produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with incorrect spelling/punctuation in a source text produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with odd word choice in a source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with misuse of vocabulary in a source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with odd style in a source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with inappropriate register shifts in a source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with lack of logic in a source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with vagueness in a source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with lack of cohesion in a source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with poor organization in a source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with unclear pronoun reference in a source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with awkward sentence structures in a source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with grammatical errors in a source talk/text produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with unconventional use of metaphors and/or concepts in a source talk/text produced by a non-native speaker?

How do you cope with these other difficulties in a source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker?

50%

Apart from having to deal with texts/talks produced by non-native speakers of English, how often are you otherwise exposed to English produced by non-native speakers in your work setting (e.g. in contact with commissioners, providers, clients or colleagues)?

- several times a day
 daily
 several times a week
 weekly
 less than once a week

How often are you exposed to English produced by non-native speakers outside of your work?

- several times a day
 daily
 several times a week
 weekly
 less than once a week

In what modality (or modalities) are you usually exposed to non-native English outside of your work context?

- reading
 conversation
 listening (podcasts, etc)
 social media/chats
 internet browsing
 movies/TV shows /YouTube/series
 other

Other (please specify):

Do you prefer to translate/interpret texts/talks produced by native or non-native speakers? (This and the following questions relate to the texts and/or speeches that you deal with in your work setting.)

- native
 non-native
 no preference
 it depends
 other

What does it depend on?

Other (please specify):

In what ways can texts/talks produced by non-native speakers be easier to work with? Multiple answers are possible.

- simpler sentence structures
 more frequent words
 lower information density
 repetitions
 slower delivery
 not easier at all
 other

Other (please specify):

60%

Do you find it easier to understand non-native English produced by someone whose first language is a language you also know?

- yes
 sometimes
 no
 I don't know

Do you prepare differently if you know that there will be non-native speakers of English?

- yes
 sometimes
 no
 I don't know

If yes: In what way?

If you translate/interpret a poor source text/talk produced by a non-native speaker, do you try to make your target text/rendition (multiple answers possible)...

- an absolute equivalent of the source text
 more understandable
 clearer
 smoother
 better style
 better structured
 other

Other (please specify):

Do you do the same for poor source texts produced by a native speaker?

- yes
 sometimes
 no
 I don't know.

How do you find dealing with source texts/talks produced by non-native speakers of English compared to those produced by native speakers of English? Multiple answers are possible.

- more difficult
 more stressful
 more effortful
 more tiring
 more unpleasant to work with
 more frustrating
 no difference
 easier
 less stressful
 less effortful
 less tiring
 more interesting to work with
 more satisfying
 other

Other (please specify):

How confident do you feel that you generally understand the intended meaning of a text produced by non-native speakers of English?

not confident at all very confident

(Place a mark on the scale above)

70%

Do you adapt your translation/interpreting for a target audience/client that does not speak English as a native language?

- yes
 sometimes
 no
 not applicable

Do you feel that frequent exposure to text/talks produced by non-native speakers affects your written and/or spoken English?

- yes
 to a certain extent
 no
 not applicable

In what way?

Do you feel that exposure to texts/talks produced by non-native speakers affects your understanding of English produced by non-native speakers?

- yes
 to a certain extent
 no
 I don't know

In what way?

Do you think that your clients' expectations concerning your English have changed since you started working as a translator and/or interpreter?

- yes no I don't know

How have their expectations changed?

Do you think that your own expectations concerning your English have changed since you started working as a translator and/or interpreter?

- yes no I don't know

How have your expectations changed?

Do you find it easy to deal with the English texts/talks produced by speakers of (multiple answers possible) ...

- your first language(s)
 languages similar to your first language(s)
 English as a first language
 any language other than English
 other

Other (please specify):

Do you find it difficult to deal with the English texts/talks produced by speakers of (multiple answers possible) ...

- your first language(s)
 languages similar to your first language(s)
 English as a first language
 any language other than English
 other

Other (please specify):

Based on your personal experience, would you say that there are fewer assignments because more events are English-only?

- The number of assignments has increased.
- The number of assignments has decreased.
- The number of assignments has remained the same.
- I don't know.

Would you say according to your experience that there are fewer booths for language pairs not involving English?

- yes
- no
- I don't know

Based on your experience, would you say that the number of interpreting assignments involving non-native speakers of English has...?

- increased
- decreased
- remained the same
- I don't know
- not applicable

Do you think that the increased use of English has had any impact on your level of job satisfaction? If so, in what way?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

In what way?

80%

Have you ever heard of English as a lingua franca (ELF)?

- yes
 no

Where did you hear about it? Multiple answers are possible.

- on the internet
 from colleagues
 during my translator/interpreter training
 from my employer
 in a specialized journal
 from a professional association
 other

Other (please specify):

Do you think that the spread of English as a lingua franca (ELF) is an opportunity or a risk for your profession?

- It's an opportunity.
 It's rather an opportunity.
 It's both an opportunity and a risk.
 It's rather a risk.
 It's a risk.
 I don't know.

It's an opportunity because....

It's rather an opportunity because....

It's both an opportunity and a risk because....

It's rather a risk because....

It's a risk because....

Do you think that your status as an interpreter/translator has changed since English has become more important in the world?

- yes; it has become higher
 no; not at all
 no; not since I started working
 yes; it has become lower
 I don't know

90%

Would you be interested in learning more about ELF?

- yes
 no
 I don't know

Please specify which aspects:

- in general
 with regard to translation practices
 with regard to interpreting practices
 other

Other (please specify):

Do you think that ELF-specific practices should be included in translation and/or interpreting training?

- yes
 no
 I don't know

Which aspects would you suggest?

What advice would you give to new translators or interpreters with regard to texts produced by non-native speakers of English?

Are there any other questions or aspects that you would have liked to see in this survey?

Are there any comments that you would like to make about the survey itself?
